

OXIDATION MECHANISM OF SiC-COATED CARBON / CARBON COMPOSITES

Xiaoqi Zhu, Zheng Yang, Hejun Li, Mokuang Kang
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
Northwestern Polytechnical University
Xi'an, Shaanxi, 710072, P.R.China

ABSTRACT

Various SiC-coated carbon/carbon composites are prepared. The weight loss curves at different temperature are measured and studied. The results show that the oxidation behavior of SiC-coated c/c is also subject to three-stage mechanism. The final stage is controlled by diffusion process. The weight loss percentage of c/c with sealed SiC coating is less than 1.2% after oxidize for 10 hours at 1500°C.

INTRODUCTION

The carbon fibre/carbon matrix composites (c/c) are now being used in such systems as rocket nozzle, reentry shield of space vehicle, disk brake and heating element. Despite their numerous advantage like low density, superior mechanical strength even at more than 2000°C high temperature and excellent friction behavior, they exhibit a fatal drawback—very low oxidation resistance. In the absence of a protective coating, c/c will oxidize rapidly in air at temperature as low as 500°C. The study of c/c oxidation behavior and mechanism is very important for its application and development.

After studying the oxidation behavior of general carbon material, P.J.Walker put forward the three-stage oxidation theory [1,2]. Dacic reported the oxidation mechanism of c/c in air. The c/c specimen he used is fabricated from the PAN carbon fibre and propylene by CVD. The results show that the oxidation process are also divided into three stage. The burning rate is determined by the chemical reaction rate at low temperature, by the diffusion rate at higher temperature and by the chemical reaction rate again at the final stage [3]. However, there is no generally accepted oxidation theory for coated c/c material. The experiment results are quite different according to different reports [4,5].

In this study, the weight loss curve of various SiC-coated c/c at various temperature are measured and compared [6].

EXPERIMENT

The specimens include unmodified c/c with SiC coating (1#), modified c/c with SiC coating (2#) and with sealed SiC coating (3#). The c/c specimen are fabricated by normal technology but modified by additives B_2O_3 , SiC and SiO_2 . SiC ceramic coating is produced on the surface of c/c composites by cementation method. The specimens are contacted with a particular composition, which is heated and maintained between $1500^\circ C$ and $2000^\circ C$ in argon atmosphere for a period to form SiC coating having the desired thickness on the c/c surface. The optimal thickness is about $50 \mu m$, which is determined by several factors including the time-temperature profile (TTP). The TTP should be arranged as the step curve to get suitable thickness.

The main reason for SiC coating failure in the past was the thermal expansion mismatch between SiC and c/c. The thermal stress is larger than the binding strength and induce crack. In this study, the pretreatment technology are adopted to enhance the binding strength of coating and relieve the internal stress.

However, it is also inevitable to eliminate crack completely in the coating by cementation technology. It is necessary to have a aftertreatment for coating. Two-step aftertreatment are used to seal the crack. The first step is to produce SiO_2 film by sol-gel technology. The second step is to seal crack furtherly by melten film. The mechanism of sol-gel technology is to obtain oxide film coating by hydrolysis and pyrolysis.

The weight loss curves of various specimens at temperature from $1000^\circ C$ to $1800^\circ C$ are measured and studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from specimen 1# and 2# (Fig.1 and Fig.2) show that the whole oxidizing process is also divided into three stage. The burning rate is constant at low temperature and initial oxidizing stage (the weight loss percentage is less than 20%). At second stage, the burning rate is also constant, but higher than the first one (the weight loss percentage is between 20% and 70%). At third stage, the weight loss percentage has logarithmic relationship with time (the weight loss percentage is higher than 70%). The burning rate of 2# is significantly less than 1#, which means matrix modification can greatly enhance the oxidation resistance of c/c. The Arrhenius curve of 1# and 2# are shown as Fig.3 and Fig.4. It is found that the first stage of Arrhenius curve is composed of two broken lines. The values of activation energy of these four parts are 158 KJ/mol, 82 KJ/mol, 79 KJ/mol and 22 KJ/mol respectively. The transition temperature is $1125^\circ C$. For 2# specimen, values of activation energy are 159 KJ/mol, 83 KJ/mol, 81 KJ/mol and 24 KJ/mol respectively. The transition temperature is $1200^\circ C$. For 3# specimen, the weight loss percentage is less than 1.2% after 10 hours oxidizing at $1500^\circ C$. The whole burning rate is constant. Its value of activation energy is 162 KJ/mol.

The oxidation procedure of coated c/c should include following steps:

1. The gas diffusion through surface border
2. The diffusion through crack and opening
3. The diffusion through the coating itself
4. The chemical reaction of oxygen and carbon [7]
5. The diffusion through the gas layer on the interface between coating and matrix. When the oxidation begin, a gas layer will be formed on the interface between coating and matrix.

Fig. 1. The Weight Loss Curve of Specimen 1#

Fig. 2. The Weight Loss Curve of Specimen 2#

Fig. 3. The Arrhenius Curve of Specimen 1#

Fig. 4. The Arrhenius Curve of Specimen 2#

Anyone of above five steps will control the whole burning rate. The determine stage is just as the stage with the slowest rate. The different value of activation energy means different mechanism. At initial linear stage, the diffusion rate is higher than the chemical reaction rate and there is no gradient of oxygen concentration in the diffusion tunnel. The burning rate of this stage is determined by the reaction. At the second stage, reaction rate increase with temperature, even higher than diffusion. The reaction mechanism begin transform to diffusion mechanism. At the last stage, after many opening and cracks have been formed, the process is almost completely controlled by the diffusion process.

It can be demonstrated that the diffusion through the interfacial gas layer is the slowest process and the burning rate \dot{M} is:

$$\dot{M} = dM / dt = K / \delta t$$

Where δt is the thickness of gas layer, K is constant. And it is supposed that

$$\delta t = K_1 \exp(K_2 M)$$

It will be

$$\dot{M} = K \cdot K_1^{-1} \exp(-K_2 M)$$

$$\ln \dot{M} = A - K_2 M$$

That means the logarithm of burning rate is proportional to the weight loss [6].

In order to verify the above analysis, the data of burning rate are differentiated with respect to time and taken the logarithm. It is shown from linear regression that $\ln \dot{M}$ and M have linear relationship. The correlation coefficient is 0.95 [6].

CONCLUSIONS

The oxidation behavior of SiC-coated c/c is also subject to three-stage mechanism. At initial linear stage, the burning rate is constant and determined by the oxidizing reaction rate, which value of activation energy is about 160 KJ/mol. At second stage, the burning rate is also constant and is not only determined by chemical reaction, but also by diffusion of O₂, CO and CO₂ through coating and matrix. The value of activation energy is between 70 KJ/mol and 100 KJ/mol. The lower value means more effect from the diffusion. At final stage, the burning rate is determined completed by the diffusion process through interface layer between coating and matrix. The weight loss percentage has logarithmic relationship with time and the logarithm of burning rate is proportional to the weight loss. The value of activation energy is less than 30 KJ/mol.

The weight loss percentage of c/c with sealed SiC coating is less than 1.2% after 10 hours oxidizing at 1500°C.

REFERENCES

1. P.L.Walker, Jr., F.R.Rusinko, Jr. and L.G.Austin, *Advances in catalyst*, **11**, 133-221 (1969) Academic Press, New York
2. I.M.K.Ismail and P.L.Walker, Jr. *Carbon*, **27**, 549 (1989)
3. B.Dacic and S.Marinkovict, *Carbon*, **25**, 409-415 (1987)
4. I.R.Strife, J.E.Sheehan, *Ceram.Bull.*, **67**,309 (1988)
5. T.Cordero, P.A.Thrower and L.R. Redavic, *Carbon*, **30**, 365-374 (1992)
6. Xiaoqi Zhu, Ph.D. Thesis (1995), Northwestern Polytechnical University
7. Krishan L.Luthra, *Carbon*, **26**, 218 (1988)